

Cryptobazar Fund

Oleg Ivanov, Andrey Yudin^a

^a *Co-founder and CEO of CryptoBazar Fund, Hong Kong*

Keywords:

1. Introduction

•Entrepreneur, investor, founder and general director of InvestBazar Fund - 0.7 billion rubles. in management. •Entrepreneurial and management experience in projects from the start-up phase to the annual revenue of \$ 1.7 billion since 1998 in 20 countries: USA, Germany, Great Britain, Ireland, Portugal, Croatia, Greece, Turkey, Cyprus, Saudi Arabia, UAE, Cote D'Ivoire, Cape Verde, Vietnam, Belarus, Ukraine, Kazakhstan, Azerbaijan, Moldova and Russia. •Founder of the energy drink Tornado; reached the 5th place in the share of sales in the category of energy drinks in Russia after the digging of Coca-Cola, PepsiCo, RedBull and Carlsberg; sold the company to a strategic investor in 2 years; Today Tornado is sold in Russia, CIS, Switzerland and the UK. •Attracted investments in its own projects for more than \$ 90 million. He trained more than 500 entrepreneurs, who in total attracted more than 1 billion rubles to their business projects. •MBA degree in Finance & Investments Netherlands. Author of the book "Operational Marketing: FMCG systems for selling, distributing, merchandising" Global Team Press, NY 2004. Leading TV and radio show about business and investments.

Expert topics: - Investing in projects before entering ICO - Attracting investments - Private investment - Business development at different stages - Project Management - Re-branding
- Marketing strategies - Commercial development - Crypto currency market - How to make money on investments in real business - How to make money on investments in cryptocurrencies

Co-founder of CryptoBazar Fund: investments in crypto-currency infrastructure projects, ready to enter the ICO in the spheres of: connection with payments in the real world, backbone projects, exchanges, banks, funds, infrastructure development, new types of blockages, technological innovations. A private investor in the real business sector since 2000 and the crypto market since 2013. The volume of investments is \$ 2 million. •Ex-CTO Mail.Ru Group •Founder and Director for Business Development "GD-Team", •Founder and Director for Business Development Business Technologies. •Founder and ex-CEO of Mastak.ru, •Founder of the ISDEF.

Winner of Google Best Global Startup 2015, participant of Google Campus Tel Aviv startup space 2016 Expert in Business Development and Software Development.

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Expert topics: - Technical arrangement of the block, - Crypto currency - Conducting an ICO - Investing in projects before entering ICO - Finance and business models

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